

HOW IS THE ROLE OF BURNOUT SYNDROME, ORGANIZATIONAL COMMITMENT, AND JOB INSECURITY ON TURNOVER INTENTION AT HASANUDDIN UNIVERSITY HOSPITAL IN 2024

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DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.12800315](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12800315)

Abstract

Background. The stability of organizational effectiveness and productivity is influenced by several factors, one of them is human resources. The most common human resource issue in hospitals is related to nurse turnover rates. **Aim.** This study aims to determine the influence of burnout, organizational commitment, and job insecurity on turnover intention at Hasanuddin University Hospital. **Method.** The research method used is a quantitative approach with a cross-sectional study design, and data collection was carried out using questionnaires distributed to all nurses at Hasanuddin University Hospital. The research sample was selected using a total sampling method consisting of 175 nurses. **Result.** The results showed that burnout affects both turnover intention and organizational commitment, while job insecurity only affects turnover intention and does not influence the organizational commitment factors. The indirect effect analysis between burnout and turnover intention showed that the indirect influence of organizational commitment was greater compared to the direct influence of burnout on turnover intention. Otherwise, the direct effect of job insecurity on turnover intention was higher than the indirect effect through organizational commitment. **Conclusion.** Organizational commitment has the greatest influence on turnover intention. To enhance this commitment, structured career development programs, effective reward systems, and PPPK appointments are necessary. Future research should include psychological factors and work-life balance for a comprehensive understanding of nurses' conditions.

Keywords: Burnout Syndrome, Organizational Commitment, Job Insecurity, Nurse.

INTRODUCTION

The stability of organizational effectiveness and productivity is influenced by several factors, one of them is human resources. The goal of an organization is to realize the aspirations of its members by involving human resources as a key element in achieving success. One common issue in human resource management is turnover, which is the resignation of employees from the organization. Fishbein and Ajzen's theory highlights that the intention to leave an organization (turnover intention) is often a major predictor of actual turnover (1). Data obtained from Hasanuddin University Hospital show fluctuations in nurse turnover rates from 2021 to 2023.

Table 1: Nurse Turnover Rates at Hasanuddin University Hospital, 2021 – 2023

No	Nurse Turnover Rates at Hasanuddin University Hospital, 2021 – 2023				Standard
	Year	Number of Nurses	Nurses Leaving	%	
1.	2021	182	8	4,40	5-10 %
2.	2022	188	28	18,90	
3.	2023	191	22	11,05	

Source: *Hasanuddin University Hospital data, 2021 - 2023*

Nurses are the largest group in the global healthcare workforce, providing around 90% of primary health services (2). Despite of this, the nurse turnover rate is quite high, with approximately 19.7% of nurses leaving their jobs within 18 months (3). High turnover can lead to organizational instability and reduce effectiveness, productivity, and service quality in hospitals. The costs incurred to recruit, train, and integrate replacement nurses into the hospital also increase significantly (4,5). According to data from Nursing Solutions Inc (NSI) in the US, the average cost per departing nurse is \$52,350. For hospitals with a turnover rate of 22.5%, this could result in potential annual losses of up to \$6.6 million (6).

Nurses serve as the frontline in hospital services and play a vital role, yet they often endure high workloads that can cause physical and psychological fatigue, potentially leading to burnout. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), burnout is a syndrome caused by chronic work-related stress. WHO recognizes burnout as a serious health problem and encourages the development of workplace mental well-being based on existing evidence (2). Meta-analysis studies reveal that around 11.23% of nurses worldwide experience significant burnout symptoms, indicating that roughly one in ten of nurses globally suffer from severe burnout (7). Longitudinal research in San Francisco also highlights high levels of burnout and turnover rates among doctors and primary care staff, emphasizing that burnout and low employee engagement contribute to high turnover rates (8). Recent studies at Hasanuddin University Hospital indicate that about one-fifth of nurses experience burnout, with some facing personal burnout, work-related burnout, and patient-related burnout (9).

For decades, the antecedents of nurse turnover have been studied, and the results indicate that job satisfaction and organizational commitment are important antecedents of nurse turnover (10). Although job satisfaction and organizational commitment are considered major determinants of turnover, a meta-analysis by Griffeth et al. (2000) shows that organizational commitment is a higher predictor of turnover intention compared to job satisfaction (11). This finding was replicated by Ingersoll et al. (2002) in a sample of nurses, yielding similar results. Research on organizational commitment shows that the stronger a nurse's commitment to their hospital, the less likely they are to intend to leave (11,12).

Organizational commitment is demonstrated by prioritizing obligations and tasks when the organization's values align with the individual's values. This affects employee performance, activity, attendance, and engagement within the organization. Nurse attendance summary related to leave and absences obtained from Hasanuddin University Hospital show an increasing trend in absenteeism each year. The average absenteeism rate for nurses at Hasanuddin University Hospital was 10% in 2021, then increased by 7% to 17% in 2022, and rose again to 24% in 2023.

Job insecurity is a psychological state where individuals feel anxious, threatened, or vulnerable due to a fluctuating or unstable work environment. Increased feelings of insecurity influence each individual's turnover intention (13). Hasanuddin University Hospital implements a contract system for nurses for a certain period as agreed by both parties. This non-permanent employment system increases job insecurity among nurses. Data on actual turnover at Hasanuddin University Hospital shows that 64.2% of nurses left because they passed the civil servant test.

As we know, the interest in registering as a civil servant (PNS) in Indonesia is very high, influenced by various factors. Civil servants are considered to have high job stability and relatively better job security compared to the private sector. Although civil servant salaries are not always comparable to those in the private sector, the continuity of salaries, benefits, and other facilities makes becoming a civil servant still attractive (14,15)

Given the turnover rate issue among nurses at Hasanuddin University Hospital, researchers aim to conduct further analysis on the variables of burnout syndrome, organizational commitment, and job insecurity in relation to turnover intention. This analysis is intended to mitigate the losses resulting from high turnover rates early on, thereby enhancing service productivity at the hospital

LITEERATURE REVIEW

Burnout Syndrome

Schaufeli and Buunk (2004) define burnout syndrome as a form of exhaustion that can manifest in physical, behavioral, motivational, cognitive, and affective aspects resulting from pressure in work situations with high emotional demands (16). According to Maslach & Leiter (2016), burnout syndrome is a psychological syndrome encompassing various dimensions, namely exhaustion, cynicism, and professional efficacy. Exhaustion is an interpersonal dimension of burnout characterized by feeling drained both emotionally and physically. Cynicism encompasses negative responses to work with more indifferent behavior and distancing from the work environment, while professional efficacy involves feelings of competence and productivity at work (17).

Organizational commitment

Organizational commitment reflects the close relationship between individuals and organizations in terms of enthusiasm, loyalty, and active participation supporting organizational goals and development. This indicates that commitment to the organization is not only a formal status but also involves deep emotional and behavioral aspects from the organization members (18–21).

According to Meyer (2014), there are three types of "mindset" indicators that describe individual commitment to the organization: Affective Commitment, Continuance Commitment, and Normative Commitment (22). Affective Commitment is the alignment of personal values with organizational values, leading to affection for the organization (23,24).

Continuance Commitment is the awareness of limited alternatives, making individuals always evaluate the pros and cons of leaving the organization. Normative Commitment is a commitment based on moral responsibility and a sense of "obligation" felt by employees towards their organization (20,25).

Job Insecurity

Job insecurity refers to a state in which individuals feel anxious about the possibility of losing their job or facing demotion, along with other threats to job stability that negatively impact psychological well-being and job satisfaction. This understanding also includes the individual's subjective experience of potential job loss risk in the future and a sense of powerlessness in maintaining job stability (26–28). Hellgren et al. (2006) divide job insecurity into two dimensions: qualitative and quantitative job insecurity (27).

Quantitative job insecurity includes worries about the possibility of losing the job itself or aspects related to job continuity in general. Meanwhile, qualitative job insecurity encompasses worries about the deterioration of job aspects such as reduced work hours, work schedule changes, income decreases, and reduced professional status. Research results show that job insecurity can negatively impact employee performance and increasing turnover intention.

Turnover Intention

Employee turnover intention is defined as the tendency or deliberate intention of employees to leave an organization. According to Mobley (1977), the decision to leave the organization is a gradual process that includes thoughts of resignation, the intention to find alternative jobs, and the evaluation of the possibility of leaving the organization. This process is complex and involves various stages, such as dissatisfaction with work, intention to leave, looking for alternative jobs, and comparing job alternatives before making the decision to resign (29).

Studies have shown that turnover intention can be influenced by various factors, such as burnout, organizational commitment, job insecurity, job satisfaction, work environment, compensation, and career development opportunities. Turnover intention is often used as a predictor of actual turnover behavior, and high turnover intention can indicate potential future turnover problems for organizations.

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1: Research Conceptual Framework

RESEARCH METHODS

Research Design

This research is quantitative and employs observational analysis with a cross-sectional approach, where the research design focuses on testing the relationship between independent variables and dependent variables at a specific point in time.

Research Location and Time

This research was conducted from May to June 2024 at Hasanuddin University Hospital.

Populations and Samples

The population targeted in this research includes all active nurses at Hasanuddin University Hospital, totaling 175 individuals, both civil servants and non-civil servants.

Data Collection

In this research, data is divided into two types: primary data and secondary data. Primary data was obtained through the distribution of questionnaires (via Google Forms and physical questionnaires) containing questions and statements related to the research variables (burnout, organizational commitment, job insecurity, and turnover intention), including the respondents' individual characteristics. Meanwhile, secondary data includes information obtained from Hasanuddin University Hospital.

Data Analysis Methods

In this research, data analysis was conducted after the questionnaire data was collected and then rechecked for completeness. Once the data was fully collected and tabulated based on the sub-variables studied, calculations were performed using SPSS software. The data analysis is divided into three types: univariate, bivariate, and multivariate analysis.

Univariate analysis is conducted by observing the frequency distribution and percentage related to the research objectives to provide a general overview of the issue being investigated. Bivariate analysis is conducted to explore the relationship or impact of independent variables on the dependent variable. The statistical test applied in this analysis is the Chi-Square test.

The Chi-Square test is used to assess the relationship between categorical independent and dependent variables with nominal scales. Multivariate analysis on the variables affecting turnover intention at Universitas Hasanuddin Hospital is conducted to explore the patterns of influence among variables. The Path Analysis method was chosen to map the most effective and direct path from exogenous variables to related endogenous variables.

The advantage of Path Analysis lies in its ability to analyze more complex models, which cannot be achieved using multiple linear regression. Path Analysis also provides insights into both direct and indirect relationships and influences, including through intervening variables.

RESULT

Respondent Characteristics

Table 2: Distribution of Respondents Based on Characteristics at Hasanuddin University Hospital in 2024

No	Respondent Characteristics	Number (n)	Percentage (%)
1	Age	20-35 years	136 77,71%
		36-45 years	33 18,86%
		> 45 years	2 1,14%
2	Education	Diploma	20 11,43%
		Ners Profession	108 61,71%
		Master's Degree	9 5,14%
		Others	38 21,71%
3	Marital Status	Married	114 65,14%
		Single	59 33,71%
4	Work Experience	1-5 years	59 33,71%
		6-10 years	76 43,43%
		11-15 years	40 22,86%
5	Career Level & Competence	Clinical Nurse I	56 32%
		Clinical Nurse II	39 22,29%
		Clinical Nurse III	76 43,43%
		Clinical Nurse IV	2 1,14%
		Clinical Nurse V	0 0%
6	Employment Status	Civil Servant	16 9,14%
		Permanent Non-Civil Servant	46 26,29%
		Non-Permanent Non-Civil Servant	113 64,57%

Source: Primary Data

Based on the distribution table regarding respondent characteristics at Hasanuddin University Hospital in 2024, it can be seen that the most common age group is 20-35 years, totaling 136 people (77.71%). Regarding gender, according to the obtained data, 82.29% are female (144 people). Most respondents are graduates of the Ners profession with 108 people (61.71%), followed by Diploma with 20 people (11.43%), and Master's Degree with 9 people (5.14%). Additionally, the majority of respondents are married. Respondent characteristics based on work experience, other workplace, and income show that most respondents have worked for 6-10 years, do not have another workplace besides Hasanuddin University Hospital, and have an average income of Rp. 2,500,000 – Rp. 5,000,000. The career level system for nurses refers to the competency level that determines the nurse's position in providing nursing care within the limits of authority regulated in the form of a career ladder. The distribution of respondents at Hasanuddin University Hospital shows that most nurses are at Clinical Nurse I level with 56 people (32%), and the lowest number is at Clinical Nurse IV level with 2 people (1.14%). The employment status of nurses at Hasanuddin University Hospital is divided into Civil Servant, Permanent Non-Civil Servant, and Non-Permanent Non-Civil Servant. Most respondents are Non-Permanent Non-Civil

Servants with 113 people (64.57%) and Permanent Non-Civil Servants with 46 people (26.29%). The majority of respondents work in the inpatient unit.

Bivariate Analysis

Table 3: Results of the Bivariate Analysis of Burnout, Organizational Commitment, and Job Insecurity on Turnover Intention at Hasanuddin University Hospital Makassar in 2024

			Turnover Intention		Total	p value
			High	Low		
Burnout	High	n	7	3	10	0,002
		%	70,0%	30,0%	100,0%	
	Low	n	35	130	165	
		%	21,2%	78,8%	100,0%	
Organizational Commitment	High	n	1	102	103	0,000
		%	1,0%	99,0%	100,0%	
	Low	n	41	31	72	
		%	56,9%	43,1%	100,0%	
Job Insecurity	High	n	12	23	35	0,170
		%	34,3%	65,7%	100,0%	
	Low	n	30	110	140	
		%	21,4%	78,6%	100,0%	
Total		n	42	133	175	
		%	24,0%	76,0%	100,0%	

Table 3 shows that respondents with low burnout and low turnover intention constitute 78.8% (130 respondents). The statistical test results show a p-value of 0.002, and since the p-value is less than α ($0.002 < 0.05$), H_0 is rejected, indicating a statistically significant relationship or influence of burnout on turnover intention at Hasanuddin University Hospital Makassar.

For the next variable, organizational commitment, it is evident that 103 respondents have high organizational commitment and low turnover intention at 99% (102 respondents).

The statistical test results show a p-value of 0.000, and since the p-value is less than α ($0.000 < 0.05$), H_0 is rejected, indicating a statistically significant relationship or influence of organizational commitment on turnover intention at Hasanuddin University Hospital Makassar.

Regarding job insecurity, the research results show that 140 respondents with low job insecurity have low turnover intention at 78.6% (110 respondents). The statistical test results show a p-value of 0.170, and since the p-value is greater than α ($0.170 > 0.05$), H_0 is accepted, indicating no statistically significant relationship or influence of job insecurity on turnover intention at Hasanuddin University Hospital Makassar.

Multivariate Analysis

Multivariate analysis was conducted to identify the influence, both direct and indirect, between the variables of burnout and job insecurity on the variable of turnover intention through organizational commitment.

In this study, multivariate analysis was performed using path analysis, which aims to explain the cause-and-effect relationship between one or more variables simultaneously.

The following table 4 are the results analysis in the direct effect on the variables :

Table 4: Results of the Direct Effect Analysis of Independent Variables on Dependent Variables at Hasanuddin University Hospital Makassar in 2024

Direct Influence of Variables			Standardized	S.E.	C.R.	P	Label
Burnout	-->	Organizational Commitment	-0,318	0,037	-4,447	0,000	Direct
Job Insecurity	-->	Turnover intention	0,144	0,021	2,604	0,009	Direct
Burnout	-->	Turnover intention	0,151	0,031	2,622	0,009	Direct
Organizational Commitment	-->	Turnover intention	-0,610	0,060	-10,554	0,000	Direct

Burnout → Organizational Commitment

There is a significant negative influence of burnout on organizational commitment. The estimation coefficient of -0.318 indicates that every one-unit increase in the burnout variable will be followed by a 0.318-unit decrease in the organizational commitment variable.

The p-value ($0.000 < 0.05$) indicates a significant influence of burnout on organizational commitment at Hasanuddin University Hospital.

Job Insecurity → Turnover intention

There is a significant positive influence of job insecurity on turnover intention. The estimation coefficient of 0.144 indicates that every one-unit increase in the job insecurity variable will be followed by a 0.144-unit increase in the turnover intention variable. The p-value ($0.009 < 0.05$) indicates a significant influence of job insecurity on turnover intention at Hasanuddin University Hospital.

Burnout → Turnover intention

There is a significant positive influence of burnout on turnover intention. The estimation coefficient of 0.151 indicates that every one-unit increase in the burnout variable will be followed by a 0.151-unit increase in the turnover intention variable. The p-value ($0.009 < 0.05$) indicates a significant influence of burnout on turnover intention at Hasanuddin University Hospital.

Organizational Commitment → Turnover intention

There is a significant negative influence of organizational commitment on turnover intention. The estimation coefficient of -0.610 indicates that every one-unit increase in the organizational commitment variable will be followed by a 0.610-unit decrease in the turnover intention variable.

The p-value ($0.000 < 0.05$) indicates a significant influence of organizational commitment on turnover intention at Hasanuddin University Hospital.

Figure 2: Path Analysis between Burnout, Organizational Commitment, Job Insecurity, and Turnover Intention

In addition to using more than one independent variable, this study also used an intervening variable, namely organizational commitment. The intervening variable functions to mediate the relationship between the independent and dependent variables. The following are the results of the indirect effect analysis of the intervening variable:

Table 5: Results of the Indirect Effect Analysis of Independent Variables on Dependent Variables at Hasanuddin University Hospital Makassar in 2024

Indirect Influence of Variables	Standardized	Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Label
<i>Burnout</i> → <i>Organizational Commitment</i> → <i>Turnover intention</i>	0,182					Indirect

Burnout* → *Organizational Commitment* → *Turnover intention

The estimation value of 0.182 indicates that the indirect effect is greater compared to the direct effect. Every one-unit increase in the burnout variable indirectly contributes to an increase of 0.182 units in turnover intention through an increase in the organizational commitment variable.

DISCUSSION

Direct Influence of Burnout Syndrome on Organizational Commitment at Hasanuddin University Hospital

Low levels of burnout are often associated with high organizational commitment. Research at Hasanuddin University Hospital shows that burnout has a significant negative effect on organizational commitment, with an estimation coefficient of -0.318 and a p-value of 0.000. When healthcare workers have strong organizational commitment, they tend to be more dedicated and motivated, actively contributing to creating a better work environment, which reduces the risk of burnout. Mental health issues, including burnout, are often overlooked in the Indonesian healthcare system, leaving many healthcare workers, especially nurses, with inadequate access to mental health support. However, at Hasanuddin University Hospital, there is a highly effective BPSS (Bio-Psycho-Social-Spiritual) unit providing mental health support. Screening and educational seminars are conducted routinely every 6 months, with screening

results available within 24 hours. Employees needing support are contacted and matched with a suitable companion or coach, with flexible mentoring times according to individual needs. Hasanuddin University Hospital demonstrates high concern for the mental health of its employees, positively impacting their commitment levels. Nearly 97% of respondents are aware of the BPSS unit, and 69% have used its services, while the remaining 31% did not feel the need as they could handle their issues independently. The effective dissemination of information and program implementation at Hasanuddin University Hospital results in low burnout levels and high commitment. The research results also show that affective, normative, and continuance commitments among nurses at Hasanuddin University Hospital are within high value ranges. High affective commitment indicates a positive perception of Hasanuddin University Hospital, where nurses feel valued, recognized, and as an important part of the hospital. This positive perception helps reduce the risk of burnout (30,31).

Direct Influence of Job Insecurity on Turnover Intention at Hasanuddin University Hospital

Job insecurity and turnover intention have a strong relationship in the hospital. When nurses feel insecure about their jobs, their concerns about job stability and security increase (13). Research conducted at Hasanuddin University Hospital shows that job insecurity and turnover intention are in the low category but have a significant positive correlation. The estimation coefficient of 0.144 indicates that every one-unit increase in job insecurity will increase turnover intention by 0.144 units, with a p-value of 0.009. The decrease in job insecurity at Hasanuddin University Hospital can be explained by the increase in PPPK (Government Employees with Work Agreements) appointments. Since Hasanuddin University Hospital became a BLUD, the appointment of permanent non-civil servant employees increased from 27 people (2019-2020) to 100 people (2022-2023) in PPPK. This provides hope and confidence that Hasanuddin University Hospital offers good career paths. Social aspects, such as marital status, also have an influence. Most respondent nurses are married. Married nurses tend to seek job stability to support their families. Social support from families helps reduce stress related to job insecurity (32). Without social support, job insecurity can reduce organizational commitment. A total of 80% (140 people) of respondents strongly agree that Hasanuddin University Hospital is a good place to grow and offers good career paths, reflecting their sense of security and optimism about their future at the hospital. Confidence in career opportunities is crucial for creating a stable work environment and minimizing turnover intention.

Direct Impact of Burnout on Turnover Intention at Hasanuddin University Hospital

Burnout syndrome is defined as exhaustion observed from physical, behavioral, motivational, cognitive, and affective aspects due to job demands with high emotional pressure (16). This study shows that burnout among nurses is significantly related to turnover intention. The coefficient estimate of 0.151 indicates that every one-unit increase in burnout increases turnover intention by 0.151 units. The HR management at Hasanuddin University Hospital uses a floating system to distribute the nurses' workload effectively. The floating system, where nurses are transferred to units that need additional workforce, increases resource efficiency and the nurses' skill development. Floating helps nurses develop new skills and adapt to various patients

and work environments, enhancing their flexibility and adaptability (33). Nursing care is the primary duty of nurses, providing holistic and integrated healthcare to patients. Good nursing care practices are essential to prevent burnout. The study by Natsir et al. (2015) shows a relationship between burnout and the implementation of nursing care according to competency standards (34). As many as 73% (127 people) of nurses at Hasanuddin University Hospital are satisfied with caring for patients according to their competence, which is related to the low burnout rate at the hospital. In the burnout questionnaire section on exhaustion, 86% (151 people) of respondents gave a low score to the statement "*I feel like my time is wasted for working all day*" indicating a balance between work and personal life. This balance is essential for maintaining personal well-being and reducing the risk of burnout. The study by Esthi & Pandjaitan (2023) also states that work-life balance has a positive and significant effect on burnout; the better the work-life balance, the lower the level of burnout (35). Overall, effective workload management and work-life balance contribute to the low levels of burnout and turnover intention at Hasanuddin University Hospital.

Direct Impact of Organizational Commitment on Turnover Intention at Hasanuddin University Hospital

Organizational commitment, which includes acceptance of organizational goals, willingness to work hard, and willingness to contribute, is closely related to low employee turnover (36). Organizational commitment is assessed through three dimensions: affective commitment, normative commitment, and continuance commitment. At Hasanuddin University Hospital, the levels of these three dimensions are high, which is associated with low turnover intention. The coefficient estimate of -0.610 indicates that every one-unit increase in organizational commitment decreases turnover intention by 0.610 units, with a significant p-value ($0.000 < 0.05$). The loyalty of nurses at Hasanuddin University Hospital can be seen from the high agreement with the statement "*I was taught to always be loyal to one organization.*" The majority of respondents' tenure of 6-10 years (43.43%) also shows their long-term commitment. This high commitment plays a crucial role in reducing turnover intention, creating a stable and productive work environment. Hasanuddin University Hospital offers various significant benefits, both financial and non-financial, that enhance organizational commitment among nurses. Financial benefits such as performance incentives, bonuses, health insurance, and employment security increase nurses' economic well-being and future security. Non-financially, professional support through continuous training and skill development helps enhance nurses' competence and careers. Additionally, a better and more flexible work environment that champions labor rights and reduces excessive workloads also contributes. The questionnaire results show that many nurses agree with the statement "*One of the reasons I continue to work in this organization is that if I leave, I will lose the benefits provided by my organization that are not available in other companies.*" The fear of career uncertainty outside the organization also strengthens their continuance commitment, as evidenced by agreement with the statement "*One of the adverse effects of leaving the company is the scarcity of alternative workplaces available.*" This high organizational commitment fostered by various benefits has a direct impact on the low turnover intention at Hasanuddin University Hospital. Nurses who feel valued and secure, both financially and in their career development, tend to have low intentions to seek employment elsewhere.

Indirect Impact of Burnout Syndrome on Turnover Intention through Organizational Commitment at Hasanuddin University Hospital

Further research explores the role of organizational commitment in the relationship between burnout and turnover intention. Organizational commitment encompasses individuals' emotional, moral, and rational attachment to the organization. Yousef and Eivazaddeh (2023) found that burnout reduces organizational commitment, which then increases nurses' intention to leave their jobs (37).

The study at Hasanuddin University Hospital shows similar results, where high organizational commitment, including affective, normative, and continuance commitment, lowers turnover intention.

Data shows that nurses with high commitment feel more attached and loyal, even when experiencing burnout, due to the emotional and professional support from the organization. A study in Egypt by Karima et al. (2020) confirms that burnout negatively impacts nurses' organizational commitment, which ultimately increases their intention to leave the job.

Organizational commitment acts as a significant mediator because of the feelings of emotional attachment, loyalty, and perceptions of organizational support. At Hasanuddin University Hospital, this sense of attachment is evident from 77% of nurses who feel part of the "big family" of the hospital, and positive perceptions of organizational support reduce the desire to move jobs. Good organizational support, such as counseling services and stress management training, increases nurses' commitment to stay at work even when facing burnout.

In conclusion, organizational commitment is an important factor that mediates the relationship between burnout and turnover intention, with nurses who feel supported being more likely to stay and cope with challenges rather than seek employment elsewhere.

CONCLUSION

There is an influence of burnout on turnover intention as well as organizational commitment. Meanwhile, job insecurity only affects turnover intention and does not affect organizational commitment.

In the analysis of the indirect effect between burnout and turnover intention, it was found that the indirect effect of organizational commitment was greater compared to the direct effect of burnout and turnover intention. The opposite results occur in the variable of job insecurity on turnover intention, where the direct effect analysis shows higher results compared to the indirect effect analysis of organizational commitment.

LIMITATIONS

Some questions related to the characteristics of respondents were unanswered or missed during the questionnaire completion. This can result in incomplete data used to support the analysis in the study. Additionally, this study is cross-sectional, meaning that data is collected at a single point in time. This design does not allow for observing changes in variables over time, and thus, cannot capture dynamics or trends that may occur.

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